

Assessing the Contribution of the Level of Knowledge and Awareness of HIV and AIDS to the Effective Implementation of Desired HIV/AIDS Prevention Intervention Programs in Higher Tertiary Institutions

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Abstract:-

Background: HIV and AIDS acknowledged as one of the worst global pandemics to date, has had very severe adverse impacts on the socio-economic development and health of populations in Sub-Sahara Africa, including in Zimbabwe. On this account, the present cross-sectional, mixed-methods study considered assessing the contribution of HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness to the implementation of effective HIV/AIDS prevention interventions in limited-resource settings to reduce HIV/AIDS incidence among the population in higher tertiary institutions in Zimbabwe. The various behaviour change interventions previously introduced in the general population in Zimbabwe excluded specifically students and employees in higher tertiary institutions. The knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS, a key factors known to facilitate the implementation of effective HIV/AIDS interventions. This study's main objective is to determine the contribution of the level of HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness toward the implementation of desired HIV and AIDS interventions in higher tertiary institutions in Zimbabwe.

Method: An explanatory sequential mixed methods design was used. A sample of 314 respondents was purposively drawn from students of five universities. A structured survey questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data. Quantitative analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 2.1 produced descriptive statistic means, percentages, tables, t-tests, correlation analysis, p-values, factor analysis, and eigenvalues information. Qualitative data analysis from secondary data was facilitated by using content/thematic analysis.

Results: Contribution of the knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS to effective implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions; The respondents agreed that knowledge and awareness contribute to implementing HIV/AIDS effective interventions. Female respondents showed higher levels of HIV/AIDS knowledge but lower levels of awareness of HIV/AIDS prevention interventions than males. Correlation analysis shows significant positive relationships between the variables: knowledge, attitudes, perceptions, and social norms on HIV/AIDS,

influenced by the level of education, awareness about HIV/AIDS, and transmission modes. The study identified desirable and effective interventions as abstinence, being faithful, consistent condom use, voluntary testing, counselling, and continuous HIV/AIDS education.

Conclusion: The study concluded that factors of knowledge and awareness facilitate attitudes, and perceptions leading to behaviour practice change. Eventually contribute to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS prevention interventions in higher tertiary institutions. Implications of the study institutions could utilize information derived from students and employees to empower them with knowledge and awareness about HIV/AIDS. In addition, include a framework for implementing effective HIV/AIDS interventions and policies.

Keywords:- HIV; AIDS; adverse impact; socio-economic; interventions; knowledge; awareness; mixed methods; HIV/AIDS interventions.

I. INTRODUCTION

HIV and AIDS acknowledged as one of the worst global pandemics to date, has had very severe adverse impacts on the socio-economic development and health of populations in Sub-Sahara Africa, including in Zimbabwe (UNAIDS, 2018). On this account, the present cross-sectional, mixed-methods study considered assessing the contribution of HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness to the implementation of effective HIV/AIDS prevention interventions in limited-resource settings to reduce HIV/AIDS incidence among the population in higher tertiary institutions in Zimbabwe. The various behaviour change interventions previously introduced in the general population in Zimbabwe excluded specifically students and employees in higher tertiary institutions (NAC Report, 2019). The knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS, a key factors known to facilitate the implementation of effective HIV/AIDS interventions have been considered with other factors to affect HIV/AIDS interventions (WHO, 2017). The absence of consensus on the mediating and moderating variables that facilitate knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS to contribute to effective implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions among students in higher tertiary

institutions motivates this study. This cross sectional study seeks to establish the contribution of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS to implementation of desired HIV/AIDS interventions in higher tertiary institutions in Zimbabwe. The main research question is does knowledge and awareness of HIV and AIDS in the higher and tertiary institutions contribute to the effective implementation of HIV and AIDS intervention programmes? The following assumption was derived from the research question.

A. Statement of hypothesis

To meet the objectives of the study, the following hypothesis was formulated,

H0: The level of knowledge and awareness of HIV and AIDS in the higher and tertiary institutions does not contribute to the effective implementation of HIV and AIDS intervention programmes.

H1: The level of knowledge and awareness of HIV and AIDS in the higher and tertiary institutions contribute to the effective implementation of HIV and AIDS intervention programmes.

B. Contribution of the study

In the reviewed literature, the researcher established that most studies on HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness are from developed countries. These studies focus on the level of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS and not on the relationships among mediating variables and moderating variables involved with the intervening variable knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS. The relationships of the variables that facilitate knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS are ignored. This paper will highlight, and clarify the role of HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness contribution to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS intervention programmes in tertiary institutions. This study seeks to explore the linkage in a practical case to reconcile the gap between theory and practice.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Knowledge and awareness of HIV and AIDS

Knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS are factors that support behavioural interventions and contribute to effective HIV/AIDS interventions. Further education of HIV/AIDS characteristics, its life cycle, its existence, transmission, counselling and testing, effects, facilitates knowledge, and awareness contributes towards effective implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions. The HIV intervening variables, knowledge and awareness are moderated by communication to effect selection of the desired HIV/AIDS prevention interventions (Fisher *et al.*, 1991). The characteristics of HIV/AIDS by Fisher did not provide elements facilitating level of knowledge, and awareness of HIV/AIDS contribute to effective HIV/AIDS interventions, hence this gap needed to be addressed. CDC, (2010) knowledge involves the acquisition and assimilation of useful facts on a particular issue in different forms. The experience in HIV/AIDS comprises identifying the virus characteristics, its transmission, the illness incubation stages, infection prevention, treatment and sexual behavioural activities, attitudes and perceptions, condom use on HIV/AIDS (WHO

Report, 2020). UNAIDS Report (2019), the youngest adults lack knowledge of the modes of HIV transmission and were ill-informed of protective methods against the risk of HIV infection. The reports failed to highlight the cause among young adults of ignorance of modes of transmission and mediating variables involved with knowledge of HIV/AIDS, a gap the current study considered.

Asaduzzaman *et al.*, (2016) in a mixed-methods survey of women on the level of HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness in Bangladesh, noted the level of HIV/AIDS knowledge contributed to the prevalence of the HIV epidemic. The educational status, and mass media access were significant on perceptions, negatively affecting awareness of HIV/AIDS, leading to low adequacy of HIV/AIDS knowledge among women. Perception drives attitude leading to behaviour change, eventually seeking more knowledge about a particular situation in line with the theory of behaviour. This study was relevant to this current research in addressing knowledge and awareness, perception, HIV incidence, neglected attitude, mediating variable information on HIV/AIDS, and moderating variable communication creating a gap that the current study considered.

Azagoh-Kouadio *et al.*, (2020) a study of HIV-positive adolescents posited that the level of knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding HIV transmission was insufficient. The study failed to highlight the elements engendered by low knowledge, attitude, and practices leading to HIV transmission among the respondents. The mediating variables addressing the improvement of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS, and perception were ignored creating a gap this current study considered.

Teija Korhonen *et al.*, (2012) in a quantitative study of university students' knowledge and attitudes towards HIV/AIDS posited that students were familiar with HIV/AIDS transmission but had some misconceptions concerning HIV/AIDS in general. The study failed to articulate the misconceptions on HIV/AIDS, elements supporting the knowledge of the students. The omission of the mediating and moderating variables misdirects the identification of the elements related to changes in levels of knowledge and awareness. The study discounted the dynamics of knowledge and awareness mediating, moderating variables that facilitate the understanding of HIV/AIDS among the population. Azagoh-Kouadio (2020), studied populations with basic knowledge of HIV/AIDS, yet they exhibited a low level of understanding of HIV/AIDS transmission, making the study incompatible with the current study population. Teija-Korhonen, study population are students in university who have similar characteristics and making the study relevant for the current study.

AVERT (2018), studies on knowledge of HIV/AIDS addressed transmission modes, testing, exposure and risky behaviours that lead to contracting the virus. The sexual health services provided the necessary information on HIV/AIDS, resulting in a higher percentage of general knowledge on the nature of HIV/AIDS. In HIV/AIDS area, knowledge works together with awareness to have an impact

on reducing HIV incidence. The study failed to highlight mediating variables and moderating variables, the driving forces behind knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS.

Further, awareness of HIV/AIDS included prevention methods, treatment, care, and counselling empowerment of the affected and infected individuals (NAC Reports, 2020). Despite a high level of HIV knowledge in many parts of Zimbabwe, a cross-sectional mixed-methods study on behaviours among the people indicated no meaningful change in HIV incidence (Campbell, & Gregson, 2010). This study did not consider the mediating, moderating variables to establish the knowledge level trends, educational level and environment wherein the respondents reside.

The exclusion of mediating and moderating variables for intervening variables' knowledge and awareness leads to ignorance of the items facilitating their improvement and sustainability. A mixed-methods cross-sectional study of adolescent pupils in Ghana noted that knowledge and awareness about HIV/AIDS were crucial in preventing the spread of the virus amid high sexual activity, the imminence of contracting the disease among the study group (Oppugn Asante *et al.*, 2013).

Additionally, among the public AIDS means the same as HIV and AIDS in most African communities. The key to a high level of HIV/AIDS awareness in a population depends on knowledge of the terms applied to interpret the definition of HIV/AIDS. Baume and Jabari (2013), in their survey, noted that necessary information on the nature of HIV/AIDS was supported by numerous HIV/AIDS educational campaigns and advertisements in mass media. This indicated that 73.3% of the respondents correctly stated the meaning of the acronym HIV. Furthermore, low knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS led to a nebulous understanding of modes of transmission, exposure and risky behaviours leading to contracting HIV. The preceding studies failed to identify the mediating and moderating variables facilitating change in the level of knowledge and awareness among the population, considering knowledge as directly influencing the acceptance of HIV/AIDS programs. The mediating variables' attitudes, and the perception that influence intention to acquire more knowledge on HIV/AIDS were ignored leading to naïveté on the subject.

Oppong *et al.*, (2013) in a survey of university students in Ghana posited that students showed a high level of HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness with an inconsistent level of knowledge among the students. The students identified transmission modes and preventative measures but were misinformed about the causative agent of AIDS, an area this current study addresses. The study did not critically consider the relations of mediating variables and moderating variables facilitating knowledge and awareness to understand, and contribute to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS intervention programmes, creating a gap to be considered in the current study.

Zimbabwe Demographic and Health Survey (2015) reported that knowledge about HIV/AIDS was generally widespread and relatively high among the population. The

perception of prevention of HIV transmission among the population using a condom differed between males and females. Misconceptions about HIV transmission exist in the population (AVERT, 2013).

A cross-sectional mixed-methods study on knowledge and awareness of students in Ghana indicated the existence of expertise for HIV as a virus that replicates and lives for years in the human body with scores: female (96.7%) male (76.7%) respectively. It failed to establish the variables separating HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness programmes among the population (Oppong *et al.*, 2013). The gap in HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness needs addressing, an area this current study considers.

Oguogho Cletus (2014), in a descriptive mixed-methods study on knowledge and perception by first-year university students, established a correlation between gender and correct answers. A significant association was found ($p=0.043$) between participants' age and knowledge about HIV, indicating that as age increased, knowledge also increased. The study ignored gender and marital status with knowledge and perception, attitude, and intention, establishing the segment that needed educational assistance.

Lena Faust *et al.* (2018)'s systematic review study assessing the effect of HIV educational intervention on HIV related knowledge, condom use and HIV incidence in sub-Saharan Africa posited that interventions were effective at improving HIV related knowledge. Peer education-based interventions effectively facilitated the uptake of HIV related knowledge and increased participation in preventive measures. The study discounted knowledge, awareness mediating variables and moderating variables that facilitate uptake of interventions.

UNAIDS Report, (2015) indicated Mozambique misunderstood the transmission of HIV only through sexual activities among the population. This led to the stigmatisation of the individuals' deterring them from undertaking HIV counselling and testing (VCT). Epstein *et al.*, (2001) noted that students from rural backgrounds coming to urban life for the first time had limited knowledge of HIV/AIDS information because their communication media faced challenges in disseminating information and was perhaps outdated.

B. Transmission of HIV/AIDS

Haroun *et al.*, (2016) in a cross-sectional survey of students at a university in the United Emirates, noted that students had knowledge and awareness of HIV and AIDS. The findings indicated students had knowledge of HIV infection, transmission modes and prevention interventions available. The students had misconceptions about transmission modes; the use of public toilets and mosquito bites. Results on getting infected with HIV through the use of public toilets, 31.9% of females and 18% of males supported the notion, (a p-value of $p<0.00$), indicating higher misconceptions among females than males. Similar levels of knowledge about the methods of transmission of HIV/AIDS between male and female students showed a proportion of males believing mosquito bites were a mode of HIV

transmission with a value of $p=0.008$. In contrast, females thought that HIV could be transmitted by using public toilets, scoring a $p<0.001$ value. There were no significant differences in responses between single and married students on the methods of transmission of HIV, except married respondents being more likely than individual students to incorrectly consider that touching an HIV-positive person leads to infection (13% vs. 9%; $p = 0.032$). Female knowledge levels scored on average higher percentages compared to males in the study. The study excluded analysing the factors: mode of transmission with the age group of the population, level of education, economic, social, and technologies affecting the population’s decision-making process. Furthermore, the transmission was not classified as mediating or moderating variable making it difficult to associate its impact on knowledge. The study ignored the social norms, attitudes and perceived behaviour regarding HIV/AIDS knowledge acquired (Haroun *et al.*, 2016).

These studies’ notable gaps were: understanding the relationships of mediating, and moderating variables involved in HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness. Knowledge of HIV/AIDS is foundational in addressing ways to reduce HIV incidences within a population. Knowledge, and awareness influences sexual behaviours, exploring attitudes, perceptionstoward condom use and prevention interventions in use among the population (NAC Report, 2018. NAC (2018) findings on HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness show that these levels influence the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS programmes. Identifying the mediating and moderating variables helps monitor, and sustain these knowledge and awareness levels. Attitudes, perceptions and practices towards HIV/AIDS

interventions are results of knowledge on HIV/AIDS acquired by individuals. Previous studies ignored mediating and moderating variables supporting knowledge and awareness variables in implementing effective HIV/AIDS interventions, an area considered in the current study. This study addresses the noted gaps through factor analysis.

C. Study variables

The study variables are HIV/AIDS knowledge, and awareness as independent variables and HIV/AIDS intervention programmes are dependent variables. Figure 1 below; portrays the study variables explained in next sentences. Knowledge and awareness are associated with the following elements:age, gender, marital status, the characteristics of HIV and AIDS, the life cycle of HIV along with HIV existence, its transmission, symptoms, and the effects on the immune system. Further, the appearance of an individual who is sharing, working and socialisation with an HIV/AIDS positive person. The understanding of the preceding elements influences the attitudes as well as the perceptions of individuals facilitating an intention to behave in a particular manner. The process is portrayed by a downward arrow from knowledge and awareness to attitudes, and perceptions. The attitude and perception facilitate the intention to act or change the behaviour of an individual. This is shown by an upward arrow from attitude, perception and intention facilitating sexual behaviour. The change in sexual behaviour affects knowledge and awareness shown by the upward arrow from sexual behaviour to knowledge and awareness. This new information updates the knowledge and awareness influence on communicating the decision making of implementing effective HIV/AIDS interventions for the population.

Fig. 1: Relationship between independent variables (knowledge and awareness) and dependent variable (HIV/AIDS interventions

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed a concurrent explanatory mixed methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative research. The quantitative aspect used questionnaires for the survey. The questionnaires were distributed to 314 respondents drawn from registered students in the institutions. Of the three hundred and fourteen questionnaires, two hundred and ninety-six were returned and used for the research. The questionnaires were analysed using SPSS version 23 to produce descriptive statistics, regression analysis, factor analysis, principal components analysis for eigenvalue. The qualitative data collection used eight focus group discussions of ten participants in each group and structured interviews. Data was analysed thematically and codes were assigned to themes for analysis purpose. The final stage was the interpretation of quantitative and qualitative results involving comparison and contrast of the results to elaborate the final findings.

IV. PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS INTEGRATED BOTH THE QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE RESULTS

The research sought to assess the relationship of knowledge and awareness of HIV and AIDS and effective implementation of HIV/AIDS intervention programmes. Subsequently knowledge and awareness of HIV and AIDS have impact on effective implementation of HIV/AIDS intervention programmes.

The hypothesis being tested is H_0 that knowledge and awareness are not contributing to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS intervention programmes among students and employees in higher tertiary institutions.

The findings on the elements associated with knowledge and awareness of HIV and AIDS in the

Descriptive tables: 1 response frequencies, 2 and 4, 5.

implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions in higher tertiary institutions are presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3, 4. Tables 1 show response frequencies, 2 measured items in p-values and percentile percentage for easy analysis. These findings are aligned to demographic elements gender, age, and marital status, analysed and presented in Tables 4, 5. These tables present the level of knowledge and awareness trend among students, employees in the higher tertiary institutions. The presentation, analysis, and discussions of findings follows the descriptions of the statements on findings. For ease of analysis, the following statements explained the findings. Agreement /disagreement are synonymous with the level of knowledge and awareness. Instruments measured the level of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS towards effective implementation of the desired HIV/AIDS interventions by the following 20 items. Items measured on 7- point Likert Scale (1=Strongly Disagree to 7=Strongly Agree).

A high score indicated the positive contribution of knowledge and awareness to HIV/AIDS level towards effective implementation of the desired HIV/AIDS interventions. Low scores show a negative contribution of HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness to effective implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions in the study population. Standard deviation and variance show the mathematical dispersion of the data set relative to the mean. A low standard deviation and variance scores show that there is some convergence in the respondent’s view on the statement under consideration. A higher standard deviation and variance scores indicate that the respondents’ opinions on the statement under consideration vary significantly.

Factor and principal component analysis facilitated in extracting correlation matrix, regression analysis for the study. Factor analysis extracted elements with eigenvalue of 1 above. Significance measured by p value of less than 0.05 and above 0.05 as insignificant.

Item	Number	Agree	Disagree	Neutral
	296	%	%	%
A person diagnosed with HIV has AIDS	296	37	-	63
HIV destroys the body’s immune system causing illness to occur	296	94	6	-
HIV exists in high concentration in bodily fluids	296	86	14	-
A person living with HIV who is healthy can still transmit the virus to other people	296	96	4	-
A healthy person with a strong immune system can get HIV	296	85	15	-
A child born of an HIV positive mother will automatically be born HIV positive	296	-	73	27
You can identify HIV positive individuals based on their appearance	296	-	45	55
HIV can live in the body for years before symptoms appear	296	68	32	-
There is a cure for AIDS	296	-	85	15
HIV can be transmitted via mosquito bites	296	-	90	10
HIV can be spread by sharing of towels and utensils(cups and spoons, etc.) used by an HIV positive person (Disagree)	296	-	89	11
An HIV positive lecturer should be allowed to continue teaching my institution (Agree)	296	82	18	-

Table 1: Response frequencies on Knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS

The results for the above table were as follow:

A person diagnosed with HIV has AIDS

Disagree 63% of the respondents disagree with the statement.

Neutral 37% of the surveyed population are not sure/neutral to the statement.

HIV destroys the body's immune system causing illness to occur HIV destroys the body's immune system causing illness to occur

Agree 94% of the respondents agree with the statement

Disagree 6% of the surveyed population to the statement

HIV exists in high concentration in bodily fluids

Agree 86% of the respondents agree with the statement

Disagree 14 % of the surveyed population disagree to the statement

A person living with HIV who is healthy can still transmit the virus to other people

Agree 96% of the respondents agree with the statement

Disagree 4% of the surveyed population disagree to the statement

A healthy person with a strong immune system can get HIV

Agree 85% of the respondents agree to the statement

Disagree 15% of the surveyed population disagree to the statement

A child born of an HIV positive mother will automatically be born HIV positive

Disagree 73% of the respondents disagree with the statement

Agree 27% of the surveyed population agree to the statement

You can identify HIV positive individuals based on their appearance

Disagree 45% of the surveyed population disagree to the statement

Neutral 55% of the respondents are neutral with the statement

HIV can live in the body for years before symptoms appear

Agree 68% of the respondents agree to the statement

Disagree 24% of the surveyed population disagree

There is a cure for AIDS

Disagree 85% of the respondents disagree to the statement

Neutral 15% of the respondents are neutral with the statement

HIV can be transmitted via mosquito bites

Disagree 90% of the surveyed population disagree to the statement

Agree 10% of the respondents agree to the statement

HIV can be spread by sharing of towels and utensils (cups and spoons, etc.) used by an HIV positive person

Disagree 89% of the surveyed population disagree to the statement

Agree 11% of the respondents agree with the statement

An HIV positive lecturer should be allowed to continue teaching my institution

Agree 82% of the respondents agree to the statement

Disagree 18% of the surveyed population disagree with the statement. Findings from the frequency table 4.1 show that all age groups are aware of the effects of HIV/AIDS infections supported by high agree to responses of males (95%) and females (93%), with significant p-values < 0.05 in favour of the alternate hypothesis. Table 4.1 was further supported with table 4.1a to establish the significant elements that facilitate the variable knowledge and awareness towards contributing to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions.

Item	Male	Female	Age(years) 17-20	Age(years) 21-28	Age(years) 28+	p-value
	%	%	%	%	%	
A person diagnosed with HIV has AIDS	62	70	57	66	78	0.013
HIV destroys the body's immune system causing illness to occur	95	93	91	97	91	0.000
HIV exists in high concentration in bodily fluids	90	84	88	87	84	0.009
A person living with HIV who is healthy can still transmit the virus to other people	98	95	94	64	91	0.000
A healthy person with a strong immune system can get HIV	81	90	93	86	81	0.000
A child born of an HIV positive mother will automatically be born HIV positive	67	80	81	72	66	0.000
You can identify HIV positive individuals based on their appearance	46	64	52	57	53	0.000
HIV can live in the body for years before symptoms appear	58	79	64	69	81	0.000
There is a cure for AIDS	83	89	100	79	91	0.000
HIV can be transmitted via mosquito bites	87	94	99	87	97	0.001
HIV can be spread by sharing of towels and utensils(cups and spoons, etc.) used by an HIV positive person (Disagree)	91	88	93	88	94	0.000
An HIV positive lecturer should be allowed to continue teaching my institution (Agree)	81	85	88	84	69	0.000

Table 2: Response Frequencies: Summary of Knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS by gender and age in percentages

The frequency table 2 shows responses on knowledge and awareness by gender and age as follow: 97% of the respondents are in the age range of 21-28 years with the highest number of both male (95%) and females (93%) are significant at p- value <0.05 respectively; 3% are in age group 17-20 years and above 28 years. This age range of 21-28 years has high knowledge and awareness of the effects of HIV/ AIDS on an infected person as compared to 3% with low knowledge and awareness. The results show that all the age groups are aware of all the effects of HIV/ADS infections as indicated by the percentages of both male and female respondents and all items supporting knowledge and awareness are significant with p-values<0.05 for all the responses. Frequency responses on modes of HIV transmission are as follows male scored 87% compared to female 94% in disagreement to HIV can be transmitted via mosquito bites; male 91% compared to female 88% disagreement to HIV can be spread by sharing of towels;

male 81% and female 85% agreement to an HIV positive lecturer should continue teaching; male 81% and female 90% in agreement to A healthy person with strong immune system can get HIV. The responses on modes of HIV transmission are all significant at p-values< 0.05. Furthermore, response frequencies of the respondents show students and employees agree that knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS contribute to effective implementation of HIV/AIDS programmes. Clearly, indicating all respondents (students and employees) agree that knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS contribute to effective implementation of desired HIV/AIDS interventions in higher tertiary institutions. The findings are in support of the alternate hypothesis as indicated by the frequency responses of the respondents that is significant p-value <0.05. Table 4.1a below is an extension of table 4.1a above profiles the views of p-values to establish the significance of the items to variable knowledge and awareness.

Item	Gender <i>p-value</i>	Age(years) <i>p-value</i>	Marital status <i>p-value</i>
A person diagnosed with HIV has AIDS	0.766	0.013	0.000
HIV destroys the body's immune system causing illness to occur	0.347	0.000	0.127
HIV exists in high concentration in bodily fluids	0.019*	0.009	0.416
A person living with HIV who is healthy can still transmit the virus to other people	0.089	0.000	0.226
A healthy person with a strong immune system can get HIV	0.005*	0.000	0.741
A child born of an HIV positive mother will automatically be born HIV positive	0.005*	0.000	0.000
You can identify HIV positive individuals based on their appearance	0.002*	0.000	0.028
HIV can live in the body for years before symptoms appear	0.002*	0.000	0.000
There is a cure for AIDS	0.001*	0.001	0.654
HIV can be transmitted via mosquito bites	0.099	0.000	0.801
HIV can be spread by sharing of towels and utensils(cups and spoons, etc.) used by an HIV positive person (Disagree)	0.003*	0.000	0.870
An HIV positive lecturer should be allowed to continue teaching at my institution (Agree)	0.366	0.000	0.000

Table 3: Summary of p-values of Knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS by gender, age, marital status

*= significant: statistical significance: *p-value*, 0.05 threshold

Table 3 above profiles the views of the respondents and significance of responses. Gender, age of respondents plays an important role in establishing the elements facilitating HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness using *p-value*. The responses with *p-value* score <0.05 identified as mediating variables significantly support knowledge and awareness to contribute towards effect implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions in higher tertiary institutions. These mediating variables/elements are as follow: HIV concentration in the bodily fluids, strong immune system, appearance, no symptoms, no cure and not spread by sharing with an HIV positive person are significant scoring *p* values <0.05) in the responses. The responses are as follow:

HIV exists in high concentration in bodily fluids (significant $p < 0.05$)

A healthy person with a strong immune system can get HIV (significant $p < 0.05$)

You can identify HIV positive individuals based on their appearance (significant $p < 0.05$)

HIV can live in the body for years before symptoms appear (significant $p < 0.05$)

There is a cure for AIDS (significant $p < 0.05$)

HIV can be spread by sharing of towels and utensils (cups and spoons, etc.) used by an HIV positive person (Disagree) (significant $p < 0.05$) and any change in their status affects the contribution of knowledge and awareness to effective implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions. The preceding clearly indicates that students and employees in higher tertiary institutions agree that knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS contribute to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS prevention interventions. The preceding findings were supported with response frequencies in table 4.1 showing high response frequencies and are significant at *p-value*<0.05 as per shown in table 3 *p-values*. Further analysis using factor analysis on the items that influence knowledge and awareness is shown in tables 4, 5 to establish mediating variables.

Tables 4, 5 profile the views of the respondents on knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS on the provided opinions

Item statement	N	%	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
A person diagnosed with HIV has AIDS	296	63	1	7	2.98	2.19	4.78
HIV destroys the body’s immune system causing illness	296	94	1	7	6.128	1.109	1.231
HIV exists in high concentration in bodily fluids	296	86	1	7	5.834	1.295	1.677
A person living with HIV can still transmit the virus	296	96	1	7	6.241	1.122	1.259
A healthy person with a strong immune system can get HIV	296	85	1	7	5.925	1.472	2.166
A child born of an HIV+ mother will have HIV	296	73	1	7	2.674	1.743	3.038
You can identify HIV+ people based on appearance	296	55	1	7	3.112	1.788	3.197
HIV can live in the body for years before symptoms appear	296	68	1	7	5.044	1.928	3.719
There is a cure for AIDS	296	85	1	7	1.877	1.380	1.904
HIV can be transmitted via mosquito bites	296	90	1	7	1.759	1.316	1.732
HIV can be spread by sharing of utensils etc. used by an HIV+ person	296	89	1	7	1.791	1.334	1.779
An HIV+ lecturer should be allowed to teach at my institution	296	82	1	7	5.567	1.884	3.548
Work in the same office	296	94	1	7	6.176	1.216	1.479
Share the same bed	296	80	1	7	5.652	1.532	2.346
Use the same toilet	296	87	1	7	5.828	1.563	2.446
Eat at the same apple	296	94	1	7	6.155	1.219	1.487
Touch him or her	296	81	1	7	5.674	1.519	2.307
Share an apple	296	50	1	7	4.316	2.253	5.077
Drink from the same cup	296	69	1	7	5.241	1.909	3.646
Socialise outside of work or school	296	95	1	7	6.310	1.126	1.269

Table 4: Knowledge and Awareness of HIV/AIDS

Source: Researcher

Table 5 below is an extension of table 4 profiles principal component factor analysis of the findings on HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness. A set of twenty items in the instrument that describe the level of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS contribution towards implementing effective HIV/AIDS interventions were considered for principal component analysis. Seven items extracted and 13 were items dropped. Seven components with an eigenvalue 1 and above were extracted from twenty items. These seven components support the level of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS contributing to the effective implementation of the desired HIV and AIDS programmes in the higher and tertiary institutions in Zimbabwe. The extracted components supporting education and awareness of HIV/AIDS were:

Aware that HIV destroys the body immune system with Eigenvalue of 1.633.

Work in the same office with HIV positive person eigenvalue of 4.388,

Share a bed, toilet, and apple; eat with HIV positive person eigenvalue of 1.521.

A person diagnosed with HIV has AIDS eigenvalue of 2.310

You can identify HIV+ people based on appearance eigenvalue of 1.801

HIV can live in the body for years before symptoms appear eigenvalue of 1.186

There is a cure for AIDS eigenvalue of 1.050

Statement	Mean scores	%	Cumulative %	Principal factor analysis – eigenvalues
HIV destroys the body's immune system causing illness	6.128	94		Not extracted below 1.0 and low variance 1.231
A person living with HIV can still transmit the virus	6.24	63		Not extracted below 1.0 and low variance 1.259
Eat at the same apple	6.155	95		Not extracted below 1.0 and low variance 1.487
Aware that HIV destroys the body immune system	2.98	94	66	1.633
Share a bed, toilet, apple, eat with HIV positive person	5.652	87		1.521
Work in the same office with HIV positive person	6.176	95		4.388
A person diagnosed with HIV has AIDS	2.98	63		2.310
You can identify HIV+ people based on their appearance	3.112	55		1.801
HIV can live in the body for years before symptoms	5.044	68		1.186
There is no cure for AIDS	1.877	85		1.050
Socialise outside of work or school	6.310	95		Not extracted below 1.0 and low variance 1.269

Table 5: Factor analysis, mean scores, percentile of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS

Source: Researcher

The preceding tables 4, 5 profile that the principal component analysis extracted seven items these are mediating variables scoring a cumulative percentage of 66% in supporting variable knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS. These seven items scored p-values <0.05, indicating that they significantly facilitate knowledge and awareness in contributing to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions. In addition, the items significantly indicate that knowledge, and awareness contribute to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS intervention programmes.

The findings indicate students and employees agree that knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS contribute to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS programmes in higher tertiary institutions. Based on the above findings reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis. It shows that knowledge and awareness contribute to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS intervention programmes in higher and tertiary. These findings are in line with a study on Knowledge and awareness by *Shokoohiet al.*, (2016): and *Asaduzzaman, Higuchi et al* (2016).

V. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS

The results from table 4 show that there is a relationship between knowledge, awareness and effective implementation of HIV/AIDS programmes supported by p-value scores < 0.05 significance. These findings indicate that mediating variables at p-value <0.05 significantly facilitate HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness in contributing to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS intervention programmes at higher and tertiary. The items with an eigenvalue of one above contribute to knowledge and

awareness of HIV/AIDS prevention interventions and are significant at a p-value <0.05. These significant items are as follows (*diagnosed with HIV and AIDS has AIDS, HIV destroys the body immune system, sharing with HIV positive person, identifying HIV+ people by appearance, HIV live in the body without symptoms, no cure for AIDS*). Any positive or negative change in the item eigenvalue affects the level of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS contributing to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions. The students and employees revealed a high level of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS indicated by a response rate of 85% in agreement with the items. Females showed a high level of HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness as compared to males. Grey areas exist in HIV modes of transmission and the life cycle of the virus among the students and employees in the universities as noted from the above findings. The preceding findings show that the students and employees agreed to knowledge and awareness are contributing to the effective implementation of the desired HIV/AIDS interventions in the higher tertiary institutions in Zimbabwe. The preceding findings are in support of the alternate hypothesis on knowledge and awareness as contributory factors to the effective implementation of desired HIV/AIDS interventions in the universities.

In addition, the following are the significant items in support of variables knowledge and awareness contributing to effective implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions with the p-values:

- The respondents were in agreement (p-value at 5% level of significance) scoring (p<0.05) that HIV exists in high concentrations in bodily fluids; A healthy person with a strong immune system can get HIV; HIV can live in the body for years before symptoms appear (p<0.05), (p-value at 5% level of significance).

- Respondents were in disagreement (p-value at 5% level of significance) scoring ($p < 0.05$) with the following statements A child born of an HIV positive mother will automatically be born HIV positive; You can identify HIV positive individuals based on their appearance; There is a cure for AIDS HIV (Disagree); HIV can be spread by sharing of towels and utensils (cups and spoons, etc.) used by an HIV positive person ($p < 0.05$), (at 5% significance level).
- The above items support the variables, knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS as essential for the effective implementation of HIV and AIDS programmes in higher and tertiary institutions. The preceding findings are significant at a p-value < 0.05 in support of the Alternate hypothesis, that knowledge and awareness are contributing to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS intervention programmes in higher and tertiary. The findings suggest that students and employees agree that knowledge and awareness are contributing to the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS intervention programs in higher and tertiary institutions. Any change in the level of HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness affects the effective implementation of HIV/AIDS intervention programmes. The respondents identified elements: HIV existence in bodily fluids; a strong immune system can get HIV; HIV can live in the body for years, a child born of an HIV-positive mother will not automatically be HIV positive; cannot identify HIV positive individuals based on their appearance; no cure for AIDS HIV; HIV cannot be spread by sharing items with an HIV positive person but through infected body fluids in support of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS programs. The above-identified elements are the mediating variables that facilitate the successful implementation of HIV/AIDS interventions.

Any change positive or negative in preceding mediating variables for knowledge and awareness impact the level of knowledge and awareness in the population. The basic facts on HIV/AIDS were prevalent among the students and employees but grey areas on HIV transmission modes and treatment of opportunistic infections need to be addressed. HIV transmission and treatment of opportunistic infections are related to the behaviour of an individual. The students and employees agree to knowledge and awareness contribute to the effective implementation of the desired HIV/AIDS interventions in the institutions. The respondents showed a high level of knowledge and understanding of HIV/AIDS issues which help in implementing effective HIV/AIDS interventions for students and employees in higher tertiary institution setups. They are grey areas on HIV transmission and HIV/AIDS life cycle as indicated by low correct responses to the HIV/AIDS transmission and life cycle among the respondents. In conclusion, there are deficiencies in the level of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS interventions by age, marital status, gender, and year of study in the study population. The previous studies on knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS prevention were generalised because they disregarded the impact of the gender, age and marital status factors that this study considered to establish the groups that need more HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness.

Female respondents proved to be more knowledgeable on HIV/AIDS issues and participated more in the activities as compared to males. There is a greater relationship between the variables as denoted by a p-values range of 0.026 – 0.05. A high level of knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS exists among the population, which stands above 75%. Females have a higher level of HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness as compared to males in line with other studies done previously (UNICEF Report, 2016).

VI. CONCLUSION

The contribution of HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness towards the effectiveness of implementing the desired interventions indicate that the more people became aware of the activities, the higher their realisation of related diseases and prevention interventions availed. Principal component analysis extracted components that support knowledge and awareness of HIV/AIDS. The understanding of the extracted components facilitates the implementation of effective HIV/AIDS interventions. Any change in the composition of the mediating variables extracted in factor analysis leads to a positive or negative impact on HIV/AIDS knowledge and awareness level among the participants. The transmission of HIV through bodily fluids is clearly a grey area that needs more knowledge and awareness among respondents to reduce stigmatisation and contribute to the effective implementation of desired HIV/AIDS in the higher and tertiary institutions population.

• LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

HIV=Human immunodeficiency Virus

AIDS=Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome

• AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

All data pertaining to this study are contained and presented in this document. The authors have further information to disclose.

• AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

The authors contributed to study conception and design, participants sampling, data collection, administering the surveys, focus groups discussions, data extraction and analysis and drafting the manuscript. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

• ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Ethical clearance was obtained from the research committee of University of Lusaka.

• HUMAN AND ANIMAL RIGHTS

No Animals were used in this research. All human research procedures followed were in accordance with the ethical standards of the committee responsible for human experimentation (institutional and national), and with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as revised in 2013.

• CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

Written and informed consent was obtained from the participants prior to the study.

• CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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